

EFFECTIVENESS OF ICT INTEGRATION IN TEACHING ENGLISH TOWARDS LANGUAGE SKILLS PROFICIENCY OF GRADE 3 LEARNERS OF GENERAL LUNA CENTRAL ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effectiveness of ICT integration in teaching English towards language skills proficiency of grade 3 learners of General Luna Central Elementary School, Quezon Province, for the SY: 2024-2025. A sequential explanatory mixed method with quantitative followed by qualitative design was used to assess the English proficiency of 80 participants, with 40 in the experimental group and another 40 in the controlled group in areas such as vocabulary, grammar, reading, and writing. The study compared the results between pupils taught using ICT and those taught without it, aiming to evaluate the effectiveness of ICT integration and develop an ICT-based instructional model. Findings revealed that pupils taught with ICT demonstrated significantly higher proficiency levels across all language domains, with most achieving "Outstanding" scores. In contrast, pupils taught without ICT primarily scored in the "Needs Improvement" range, except for reading, where they achieved "Satisfactory" proficiency. The Mann-Whitney U Test confirmed a statistically significant difference in English proficiency between the two groups, indicating the positive impact of ICT on language development. Based on the results, an ICT-based instructional model was proposed, incorporating adaptive learning technologies, multimedia tools, and monitoring systems to create personalized, interactive, and flexible learning experiences while addressing potential challenges. Moreover, it reinforces the need for a technology-integrated approach in teaching English at the primary level, as it aligns with the K-12 revised and MATATAG curriculum's emphasis on contextualized, engaging, and adaptive learning

experiences that cater to diverse student needs, particularly in enhancing language proficiency that can be of used in program, project or policy development and contextualization in DepEd.

Keywords: *ICT Integration, English Language Proficiency, Language Instruction, Vocabulary, Grammar, Reading, and Writing*

INTRODUCTION

Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) are revolutionizing classrooms globally by strategically enhancing teaching and learning. ICT integration goes beyond merely using computers in schools; it involves employing technology to introduce new concepts through simulations and educational games, reinforce learning with interactive activities and quizzes, extend access to vast online information, enrich experiences with multimedia and virtual reality, and assess progress through online quizzes and collaborative projects. The benefits of ICT integration include increased learner engagement, improved learning outcomes, development of essential 21st century skills, and differentiated instruction tailored to various learning styles and paces.

In a global setting, ICT platforms such as “Kahoot” and mobile applications revolutionize language instruction, increasing learner motivation, comprehension, and achievement. It demonstrates how well ICT-based instruction may increase student involvement and transform Moroccan education, highlighting the significance of ICT integration in a globalized digital learning environment (Ennouari & Houssaini, 2023). Indeed, language learning is made fun and efficient by ICT's capacity to hold young students' interest through interactive games and multimedia materials (Chen et al., 2019; Barz et al., 2023). Furthermore, ICT offers authentic learning materials that aid in proper pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary acquisition. It also supports personalized learning, catering to individual learner needs, though overreliance on technology may affect essential teacher-learner interactions (Champa et al., 2021).

Integrating Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in English Language Teaching (ELT) has significantly improved teaching environments, enhancing blended learning, e-learning, and outcome-based education. This global trend shows that ICT in ELT boosts language proficiency, with research emphasizing that teachers must adopt technology to stay relevant. As education evolves, learners benefit from abundant resources, reducing reliance on regular teachers. ICT tools are essential for engaging learners and creating an effective learning environment (Priya & Nagarajan, 2019).

In Asia, PISA 2022 results for English proficiency in Asian countries showed that Singapore scored the highest globally in reading, including other high-performing Asian countries like Japan, Korea, and Chinese Taipei. However, many countries have low performance. These countries also performed well above the OECD average in reading proficiency, showcasing their robust educational systems. However, compared to other

countries like Thailand, Uzbekistan, and Cambodia, the Philippine students' reading scores fell short of the OECD average.

With this, there is accelerated ICT reliance in Asian EFL classrooms, revealing teachers' high ICT knowledge and highlighting challenges like limited learner technological literacy and inadequate infrastructure (Maru et al., 2021). Despite these barriers, ICT's role in enhancing learner achievement and proficiency is clear. Parveen et al. (2023) demonstrated that ICT tools redefine language instruction by accommodating diverse learning styles. Online platforms and virtual classrooms make learning accessible and engaging, exposing learners to authentic English language experiences.

Tolentino and Santos (2020) shared that a study conducted in the Philippines among graduating English majors found a disparity between confidence and proficiency in English skills, emphasizing the need for improved admission policies and ICT integration to bridge proficiency gaps and prepare learners for the work. Moreover, Gamboa et al. (2021) highlighted English's global importance and the persistent struggle with proficiency in the Philippines despite numerous interventions.

The 1987 Constitution and Republic Act No. 7104 are two legal frameworks highlighting English proficiency's importance in communication and education. DepEd regulations also support the systematic development of English language competency. The Implementing Rules and Regulations of the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 through Republic Act 10533 provides a structured approach and framework to integrating ICT in education, ensuring a standardized method across educational institutions. This is supported by the 2C2IR framework, which focuses on engaging educational content, applying ICT in relevant contexts, seamlessly incorporating it into the curriculum, encouraging innovative methods, and continuously assessing effectiveness.

ICT integration aims to enhance English language learning by making it more dynamic and engaging, thus improving learner engagement and comprehension while promoting essential 21st century skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, collaboration, and communication. Also, DepEd Order No. 6, s. 2016, sets guidelines for learner assessment in the K to 12 program and aligns with ICT integration in English classes by leveraging digital tools for formative and summative assessments. ICT enhances learner engagement and provides real-time feedback through online quizzes and e-learning platforms, which helps tailor instruction to individual needs. This integration supports the framework's goals by improving language proficiency and developing 21st century skills, ensuring that assessments are practical and aligned with curriculum objectives.

Eslit (2023) found that technology integration in ELT improves learner engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes. Interactive tools and online resources offer practice and feedback opportunities, enabling personalized instruction. However, challenges like access to technology, teacher training, and learner digital literacy must be addressed for successful ICT integration.

In the local settings, in the Schools Division of Quezon, Lopez (2022) found that ICT with instructional materials can significantly increase the learners' vocabulary and reading comprehension skills, which are significant factors in language proficiency. Further, this can be used as both an instructional and intervention activity that gives learners experience in the language with authentic spelling, meaning, grammar, and use. Moreover, Francia (2022) also found that ICT-based instructions or integration can create an interactive reading and writing learning experience centered on the learners' needs, which leads to language proficiency or communicative competence.

Aside from these, teachers in the district's elementary schools observe the learners' inclination to learn the English language and their participation and attention when ICT is used in language classes. On the other hand, not all classes used ICT integration, and minimal use was made due to facility and equipment shortages to maximize the use of ICT. Thus, the learners show up and down performance in their classes. Learners in the district, a rural town in the province, show promising language proficiency development, and they only realized a district and school low mean percentage score in examinations together with mathematics and science, which also used the English language. Likewise, in the actual school, learners are challenged with language development, which is evident in their communication in both oral and written performance. This also affects other subjects that use the English language.

The existing research highlights the benefits of integrating Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in English language teaching (ELT) across various contexts, emphasizing its potential to enhance language proficiency and engagement among learners. However, there remains a notable gap in research, specifically within the rural setting of General Luna Central Elementary School in General Luna, Quezon Province. While studies have explored ICT integration in ELT in diverse settings, including urban and national contexts, there is limited literature on its effectiveness within rural schools, particularly in the Philippines. The current study aims to address this gap by examining the effect of ICT integration on English proficiency among grade 3 learners in a rural school setting.

Thus, the researcher hopes the present study will help the learners develop English language proficiency and teacher instruction facility by integrating ICT into English language instruction in General Luna Central Elementary School, General Luna, Quezon Province. The information collected in this study would help plan teachers' development opportunities and procurement of learning materials in the delivery and implementation of the curriculum. Since there are no studies conducted yet in the school and the district on this aspect, though many are using it, this study might enlighten the researchers and teachers about the effectiveness of ICT integration in language proficiency development.

This study aims to find the effectiveness of ICT integration in developing elementary learners' proficiency in a rural school. It is very timely to conduct this study to create an intervention, instructional materials, development plans, and even policies

considering the study findings to improve and strengthen the instructional delivery and supervision of English language learning.

Research Questions

This study aimed to examine the effectiveness of ICT integration in teaching English towards language skills proficiency of Grade 3 Learners of General Luna Central Elementary School.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the English proficiency level of the learners taught in English with ICT integration in terms of:
 - 1.1. Vocabulary;
 - 1.2. Grammar;
 - 1.3. Reading and
 - 1.4. Writing?
2. What is the English proficiency level of the learners taught in English without ICT integration in terms of:
 - 2.1. Vocabulary;
 - 2.2. Grammar;
 - 2.3. Reading and
 - 2.4. Writing?
3. Is there a significant difference in the English proficiency level of the learners taught in English using ICT and those taught in English without using ICT?
4. What ICT-based instructional model in English could be developed based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

In this study, it used Explanatory Sequential Mixed Methods Design that is a research approach that begins with the collection and analysis of quantitative data, followed by a qualitative phase to provide deeper insights into the numerical findings. This design is particularly useful when researchers aim to first establish measurable trends, differences, or relationships through statistical analysis and then explore the underlying reasons, perspectives, or experiences behind these patterns. The process typically involves two distinct phases: an initial quantitative phase, where numerical data are gathered through surveys, tests, or experimental methods, followed by a qualitative phase, where interviews, observations, or open-ended responses are analysed to contextualize and explain the quantitative results. The sequential nature of this design ensures that qualitative data serves as a means of refining or interpreting the numerical findings and allow researchers to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon being studied. This design is particularly valuable in educational research,

where interventions, instructional strategies, or policy implementations often yield complex and multi-layered outcomes that require both empirical validation and experiential exploration.

This is suitable to the current study which examines the effectiveness of ICT integration in teaching English among Grade 3 learners. The post-test design only serves as the quantitative phase, where proficiency in vocabulary, grammar, reading, and writing is assessed statistically to determine the impact of ICT-based instruction. After identifying significant differences in proficiency levels, the qualitative phase follows, wherein journal entries provide insights into learners' learning experiences, challenges, and perceptions of ICT integration in English instruction. This qualitative analysis helps explain the patterns observed in the test scores, offering a deeper understanding of how ICT influences language learning beyond numerical gains. The explanatory sequential design is well-suited for this study as it not only measures the effectiveness of ICT integration but also allows for a richer interpretation of its role in enhancing language skills, leading to the development of an ICT-based instructional model that reflects both statistical evidence and student experiences.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in General Luna Central Elementary School in General Luna, within the 3rd Congressional District of Quezon Province, Philippines. General Luna is a coastal municipality with a land area of 101.02 square kilometers and a population of about 25,000. The municipality is divided into 27 barangays.

The study was conducted specifically in General Luna Central Elementary School in the center of the town. This is a población where the source of family income is farming and fishing. Most people in the province are mainly Tagalog and can hardly speak English, although they can understand it. This locale was chosen since the area's learners showed low English proficiency, likely influenced by their unique context and culture. Moreover, most of the students in the central elementary school had gadgets used for education and other purposes, making them more engaged and experienced in using ICT. The locale is in the most progressive barangay in the town, where the internet connection is always reliable.

Likewise, the learners in this elementary school from Grades 1 to 6 all showed low performance and achievement in English language classes, especially the Grade 3 learners. The learners struggled with listening, speaking, reading, writing, vocabulary, and grammar. Furthermore, despite these difficulties, the use of ICT in the teaching-learning process was still not fully implemented despite good equipment, a reliable internet connection at the town proper, and ICT-competent teachers.

Research Population and Sample

The participants in the study were the grade 3 learners of General Luna Central Elementary School, General Luna District in the 3rd Congressional District of the Division

of Quezon. A purposive sampling technique was used to select the study participants from the four (4) sections in Grade 3. Grade 3 was chosen since they were in the transition level and presented the lowest performance in the English language in the school. Classes followed heterogeneous groupings for the three sections, while one was the top section.

Therefore, the three classes had both high and low-performing students in each. From these three classes, only two sections were chosen. These classes were selected as groups, each with 40 learners. One of the three classes had more than 40 learners, which led to its elimination. From these, only the two heterogeneous classes with 40 learners were used. This approach had higher accuracy and eliminated sampling errors where participants' placement was impossible.

Research Instrument

The assessment questionnaire used in the study in the post-test was researcher-made and was subjected to tests of validation and reliability by experts. The instrument was composed of 4 parts. Part I was about vocabulary with ten questions. Part II was about grammar, with ten questions. Part III was about reading and comprehension with ten questions, and Part IV was about writing, with another 10 points rated using a rubric. Achievements on these proficiency tests were rated as Did not Meet Expectations (74.99% and below), Need Improvement (75.00%-79.99%), Satisfactory (80.00%-84.99%), Very Satisfactory (85.00%-89.99%), and Outstanding (90.00%-100%). These were based on the "Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K-12 Basic Education Program" stipulated in DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015.

Aside from these, the researcher also used observations to determine if ICT integration was effective in improving the learners' English proficiency. The English teacher in the school narrated these observations in journal form, and the teacher wrote daily reflections for specific observations.

Master Teachers validated these research instruments with a specialization in English or a master's degree in English. This increased the validity and reliability of the data gathered. Propositions and comments were integrated into the finalized instrument for utilization. After the validation of the instrument, these were pilot tested in another grade 3 class in a different school with 30 participants and were found to have excellent or high reliability with .92.00 results. Aside from the validation, experts in ICT integration in English classes were consulted in lesson planning and instructional material as well as other aspects before, during, and after the implementations. All the tools underwent face validation by an ICT expert in the district. Moreover, journal entries were used to support

the test results, this journal was made from daily observations when the ICT integration is implemented that was conducted for 4 weeks.

Data Gathering Procedure

The following procedures were undertaken in the data gathering relative to the conduct of the study: The researcher sought permission from the division office through the district and school principal to implement the research study. After approval, the researcher asked the English teacher of the central elementary school to implement the lessons with ICT integration throughout the first quarter for grade 3 using an enhanced module as instructional material. In the lesson delivery, the English teacher is observed every Friday to implement the lessons with and without ICT and provide guidance and technical assistance in all aspects of teaching.

Specifically, two sections were used in grade 3, which both use a learner-centered approach: one section for the experimental group, which used the module with ICT integration, and another section for the control group, which used the regular module and instructional materials provided by DepEd. All the sections had 40 learners. After the lesson implementation, the post-test was administered following the specifications table aligned with the Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) as a DepEd standard. During the implementation, the teacher wrote a journal (four weeks). Through this, the researcher gathered qualitative data to determine if ICT integration effectively increased English proficiency. The collected data were analysed and interpreted to assess the effectiveness of ICT integration in developing learners' language proficiency.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data gathered were tested using the following statistical tools: raw score with percentage and Mann Whitney U test.

In statement of the problem number 1 and 2, raw scores and percentages were used to determine the proficiency level of the learners after integration of ICT.

In statement of the problem number 3, to test the study hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the English proficiency level of the learners taught in English using ICT and those taught in English without using ICT, Mann Whitney U test was used for the distribution of the data is non-normal. All these were computed with SPSS, or Statistical Package for Social Sciences, using Microsoft Excel in tabulations and basic computations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Part I. English Proficiency Level of the Learners Taught in English with ICT Integration

Table 1. *English Proficiency Level of the Learners Taught in English with ICT Integration in Terms of Vocabulary*

Score Range	Frequency	Percentage	Overall Percentage Score	Mean Score	Interpretation
9 - 10	31	77.50%	90.75%	9.08	Outstanding
7 - 8	9	22.50%			

Table 1 presents the English proficiency level of the learners taught in English with ICT integration in terms of vocabulary, with an overall percentage score of 90.75%, described as outstanding. Most learners (77.5%) scored within the 9-10 range, while 22% scored 7-8. This simply means learners have exceptional achievement and mastery of English proficiency skills.

Moreover, the findings indicate that when ICT integration was used, learners showed a strong English proficiency in terms of vocabulary development. This signifies that technology in teaching significantly enhances learning outcomes by providing students with engaging, interactive environments where language skills can be developed more effectively. Through ICT, students learn at their own pace, explore vocabulary, and practice with multimedia materials like learning apps, videos, and interactive exercises. This creates a more immersive learning experience, leading to a better language understanding. While some learners still faced challenges and had lower scores, these difficulties could be attributed to variations in learning styles, limited access to technology, or lower baseline proficiency. These factors indicate that while ICT integration is effective for the majority, additional strategies may be needed to ensure that all learners benefit equally from such methods. For teachers, the result implied the importance of incorporating technology into their instructional practices to provide a more personalized and flexible learning experience. Teachers can use ICT tools to differentiate instruction, catering to different classroom proficiency levels and learning styles.

Likewise, observation results from the teacher stated the following:

1. "Learners were engaged with the PowerPoint Presentation visuals and the real-time examples. Many of them quickly grasped the concept of adding /s/ and /es/. The Quizlet activity helped reinforce the lesson by allowing them to practice matching singular and plural forms in an interactive setting."

- *(Observation No. 1, September 2, 2024 - Vocabulary: Use Plural Form of Regular Nouns by Adding /s/ or /es/)*

2. "Learners were very engaged during the Kahoot! quiz, which provided immediate feedback on their understanding. The competitive, game-based nature of the quiz helped reinforce the lesson in an enjoyable way. Afterward, they showed great creativity in their stories and sentences on Padlet, using a variety of common and proper nouns."

- *(Observation No. 2, August 30, 2024 - Vocabulary: Use Common and Proper Nouns in a Sentence)*

3. "The Kahoot! quiz promoted active participation and kept them focused while reinforcing their knowledge through an engaging format. Pupils received immediate feedback on their responses, helping them understand and correct mistakes in real-time."

- *(Observation No. 3, September 4, 2024 - Vocabulary: Use Plural Form of Regular Nouns by Adding /s/ or /es/)*

The observations highlight the effectiveness of ICT integration in vocabulary development by providing interactive, engaging, and feedback-driven learning experiences. Tools such as Quizlet, Kahoot!, and Padlet contributed to higher learner engagement, faster error correction, and more dynamic language practice. The use of instant feedback mechanisms helped learners quickly identify and correct mistakes, reinforcing their understanding of vocabulary concepts. Additionally, gamified learning through Kahoot! and collaborative digital platforms like Padlet motivated students to actively participate in exercises, fostering a deeper understanding of word meanings and usage. These findings suggest that technology-enhanced learning promotes better vocabulary acquisition, retention, and application compared to traditional teaching methods. However, the need for additional guidance for some learners indicates that variations in digital literacy, learning styles, and prior knowledge can influence effectiveness, requiring differentiated instructional strategies.

The quantitative findings in Table 1 reinforce the effectiveness of ICT integration in vocabulary proficiency, as shown by an overall percentage score of 90.75%, classified as outstanding. Most students (77.5%) scored within the 9-10 range, demonstrating exceptional achievement and mastery of English vocabulary skills. The observations in Part I support these results by illustrating how ICT tools provided engaging, self-paced learning opportunities, immediate feedback, and interactive exercises, leading to higher proficiency levels. The data confirms that technology in education significantly enhances

learning outcomes, allowing students to explore vocabulary through multimedia resources, collaborate in real-time, and practice using interactive exercises. While a small percentage (22.5%) scored within the 7-8 range, this can be attributed to differences in learning styles, baseline proficiency, or access to technology, emphasizing the need for additional scaffolding and personalized support to maximize ICT benefits for all learners.

The result validates the findings of Dash and Kuddus (2020), who emphasized the importance of technology-enhanced language learning (TELL) tools in fostering autonomous learning and improving vocabulary acquisition. Similarly, Khan and Kuddus (2020) found that ICT promotes interactive, engaging lessons that enhance language proficiency, making lessons more dynamic and adaptable to the needs of learners. Furthermore, Read Naturally (2024) highlighted that ICT-based tools help with vocabulary retention by providing incidental and intentional learning opportunities, reinforcing the importance of integrating technology into the curriculum. In the Philippine context, the Department of Education's Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 (Republic Act No. 10533) mandates the integration of ICT in the curriculum to enhance learning outcomes, particularly in language instruction. This legal framework supports the study's findings, reinforcing that ICT integration is beneficial and necessary for improving students' English proficiency. The law underscores the role of technology in making education more accessible, efficient, and tailored to the needs of diverse learners, thereby supporting the ongoing use of ICT in enhancing students' vocabulary and overall language skills.

Table 2. *English Proficiency Level of the Learners Taught in English with ICT Integration in Terms of Grammar*

Score Range	Frequency	Percentage	Overall Percentage Score	Mean Score	Interpretation
9 - 10	33	82.50%	91.25%	9.12	Outstanding
7 - 8	7	17.50%			

Table 2 shows the English proficiency level of the learners taught in English with ICT integration in terms of grammar, with an overall percentage score of 91.25%, described as outstanding. It could be gleaned that most learners scored in the 9-10 range with 82.50%, while 17.50% scored within the range of 7-8.

The results clearly show that integrating ICT in English instruction significantly enhances grammar proficiency, as students engaged more actively with digital tools that provided instant feedback, interactive exercises, and real-world applications of

grammatical rules. The technology-driven approach allowed them to practice grammar in diverse ways beyond traditional drills, making learning more engaging and reinforcing their understanding through constant exposure. However, the few students who struggled may have faced difficulties related to learning styles or accessibility, which limited their ability to maximize ICT's benefits. Given these insights, teachers should consider leveraging ICT more strategically, ensuring that digital resources are inclusive and adaptable to different learning needs. Blended learning models or personalized interventions may help address disparities, allowing all students, regardless of their technological comfort or access, to develop strong grammar skills effectively.

Likewise, the teacher observed the following:

4. "Learners were enthusiastic about creating dialogues with their partners. Most of them successfully incorporated declarative and interrogative sentences. They enjoyed sharing their dialogues and identifying the sentence types in their peers' work. Using Google Docs allowed for real-time collaboration, making it easy for them to share and edit their work. Pupils enjoyed presenting their work on the PowerPoint Presentation, which encouraged them to be more thoughtful in constructing their dialogues."

- (Observation No. 1, August 16, 2024 - Grammar: Using Different Kinds of Sentences in Dialogue)

5. "Learners showed improvement in using all four types of sentences in their dialogues. They were able to incorporate a variety of sentence types into their work, but some of them still had trouble with the flow and natural integration of all the sentence types. Google Docs allowed them to write freely and make immediate revisions to their work. Working with a partner on feedback encouraged students to reflect on their own work and enhance their understanding."

- (Observation No. 2, August 20, 2024 - Grammar: Using Different Kinds of Sentences in Dialogue)

6. "Most learners were able to revise their dialogues effectively, incorporating suggestions from peers. The use of Padlet allowed them to see a variety of approaches to using sentence types in dialogues, which enhanced their understanding. Google Docs made it easy for them to make revisions quickly, and they were able to reflect on peer feedback. Padlet provided a platform for learners to engage with each other's work, promoting further learning."

- (Observation No. 3, August 22, 2024 - Grammar: Using Different Kinds of Sentences in Dialogue)

The observations emphasize how ICT tools enhance grammar proficiency by fostering collaboration, real-time editing, and interactive learning. Digital platforms like Google Docs, PowerPoint, and Padlet enabled students to actively construct and revise sentences, helping them apply grammatical rules in meaningful contexts rather than through isolated drills. Instant feedback from digital tools and peer interactions allowed

learners to identify and correct errors quickly, reinforcing their understanding of sentence structures. Additionally, interactive elements such as PowerPoint presentations and Padlet discussions encouraged students to experiment with different sentence types, improving their fluency and grammatical accuracy. However, some students still faced difficulties with sentence flow and integration of multiple sentence types, suggesting that while ICT is highly effective, targeted interventions may be necessary for learners who require additional support in sentence construction.

The quantitative data in Table 2 strongly supports the effectiveness of ICT integration in grammar proficiency, with an overall percentage score of 91.25%, categorized as outstanding. Most students (82.50%) scored within the 9-10 range, demonstrating exceptional mastery of grammar. The observations in Part I confirm that digital tools provided learners with engaging, interactive grammar practice, allowing them to refine their sentence construction and grammatical accuracy in real time. The collaborative and feedback-driven approach enabled by ICT integration played a crucial role in reinforcing sentence structure, improving fluency, and making grammar learning more dynamic. However, a small percentage (17.50%) of learners scored within the 7-8 range, which may indicate learning style differences or challenges related to technology accessibility. To bridge this gap, blended learning models—combining ICT-based activities with direct teacher-led instruction—could ensure that all students, regardless of their comfort with technology, receive the support they need to develop strong grammar skills effectively.

These findings are supported by research highlighting ICT's effectiveness in enhancing grammar instruction. Sabiri (2020) emphasized that integrating technology into language teaching transforms regular methods, making learning more interactive and motivating for students and teachers. Similarly, Tang et al. (2021) found that ICT fosters a more engaging learning environment and helps develop students' grammatical accuracy through repeated exposure and practice in varied contexts. Additionally, Abel et al. (2025) pointed out that teacher perceptions of ICT are generally positive due to the flexibility and dynamism it brings to language instruction. In the Philippines, the Department of Information and Communications Technology Act of 2015 (Republic Act No. 10844) supports integrating technology in education, emphasizing the need for ICT to be part of the curriculum to enhance learning outcomes. This legal framework aligns with the findings, as it recognizes the transformative power of ICT in improving language instruction, particularly in developing essential language skills such as grammar. The law encourages schools to adopt ICT-based approaches to education, further reinforcing the importance of technology in promoting academic success and language mastery.

Table 3. *English Proficiency Level of the Learners Taught in English with ICT Integration in Terms of Reading*

Score Range	Frequency	Percentage	Overall Percentage Score	Mean Score	Interpretation
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9 - 10	34	85.00%	91%	9.1	Outstanding
7 - 8	6	15.00%			

As reflected in Table 3, the English proficiency level of the learners taught in English with ICT in terms of reading was described as outstanding, with an overall percentage score of 91. Most learners (85%) scored within the 9-10 range, while 15% scored within the 7-8 range. The findings indicate that learners taught in English with ICT integration exhibited a high level of proficiency in reading, with most students performing at an outstanding level.

The findings indicate that integrating ICT into reading instruction significantly enhances students' comprehension and engagement, as digital tools like interactive e-books and reading apps provide a more immersive and self-paced learning experience. These technologies have likely helped students interact more deeply with texts, offering instant feedback and supplementary resources that reinforce understanding. However, a small group of students who scored lower may have struggled due to differences in reading speed, learning preferences, or limited access to technology, which could have hindered their ability to fully benefit from digital reading tools. Given this, teachers should continue leveraging ICT to create more dynamic and flexible reading instruction while ensuring that all students, regardless of their technological familiarity, receive the support they need. Personalized reading strategies or guided digital literacy instruction may help bridge the gap, ensuring that every student can maximize the benefits of technology in strengthening comprehension skills.

In the observations, the teacher has seen the following:

7. "Learners were engaged with the story, and the use of Read&Write for Google provided accessibility features that allowed them to hear the story read aloud if needed. They demonstrated a solid understanding of the story and could identify the 2-syllable words with some guidance. The Kahoot! quiz helped reinforce their understanding in a fun, competitive way."

- *(Observation No. 1, September 19, 2024 - Reading: Read Phrases, Sentences, and Short Stories Consisting of 2-Syllable Words)*

8. "The learners performed well during the review activity, with many correctly identifying and using the 2-syllable words in sentences. The Kahoot! quiz provided a fun way for them to assess their knowledge, and most answered the questions correctly. However, a few of them still had difficulty with some of the more challenging 2-syllable words, especially those with less common vowel combinations."

- *(Observation No. 2, September 23, 2024 - Reading: Read Phrases, Sentences, and Short Stories Consisting of 2-Syllable Words)*

9. "I was impressed by how well the learners using interactive reading apps performed on their comprehension tests today. Many of them seemed to grasp the key ideas of the reading better than when we used paper-based texts. The app's instant feedback and engaging features supported their understanding of the material."

- (*Observation No. 3, September 23, 2024 - Reading: Read Phrases, Sentences, and Short Stories Consisting of 2-Syllable Words*)

The observations stress how ICT integration enhances reading proficiency by providing interactive, multisensory learning experiences. Tools like Read&Write for Google, Kahoot!, and interactive reading apps allowed students to engage with texts dynamically, reinforcing their comprehension through instant feedback, audio support, and gamified assessments. These tools helped learners decode words more efficiently, recognize patterns, and strengthen their fluency by providing scaffolding that traditional paper-based methods lacked. Additionally, the competitive and interactive aspects of Kahoot! motivated students to engage actively with reading material, making comprehension exercises more enjoyable and effective. However, some learners still faced challenges with complex vocabulary and pronunciation, suggesting that while ICT provides substantial support, personalized reading interventions may be necessary for students who struggle with certain aspects of fluency and comprehension.

The quantitative findings in Table 3 validate the effectiveness of ICT integration in reading proficiency, with an overall percentage score of 91%, categorized as outstanding. The fact that 85% of students scored within the 9-10 range demonstrates that digital reading tools contributed significantly to their comprehension and fluency. The observations in Part I support these results, showing how ICT-based interventions such as Read&Write for Google and reading apps facilitated deeper text interaction, improved comprehension, and provided immediate feedback. 15% of students who scored in the 7-8 range may have faced difficulties related to reading speed, learning preferences, or access to digital tools, highlighting the need for blended instructional strategies that combine technology with targeted teacher guidance. To further optimize learning outcomes, teachers should continue incorporating ICT in reading instruction while also ensuring that struggling learners receive individualized reading support to bridge comprehension gaps.

Previous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of ICT in enhancing reading proficiency. Wallot et al. (2019) explored how interactive technologies positively impact reading comprehension by allowing students to engage with texts more flexibly and personally. Moreover, Rustum (2021) highlighted that using popular literature and digital reading platforms can significantly improve students' reading skills by making reading more relatable and engaging. Furthermore, McKeown (2019) emphasized that using ICT tools in reading instruction encourages collaborative learning, which enhances students' ability to analyze and comprehend texts more deeply. In the Philippines, Department of Education Order No. 78, s. 2010, which emphasizes the "Strengthening of the Integration of ICT in Basic Education Curriculum." The order supports using technology to enhance literacy skills, mainly through ICT-based reading programs and interventions.

Table 4. *English Proficiency Level of the Learners Taught in English with ICT Integration in Terms of Writing*

Score Range	Frequency	Percentage	Overall Percentage Score	Mean Score	Interpretation
9 - 10	32	80.00%	91.75%	9.18	Outstanding
7 - 8	8	20.00%			

Table 4 shows the English proficiency level of the learners taught in English with ICT integration in terms of writing. Most of the learners, or 80%, scored within the 9-10 range, while eight students, representing 20.00%, scored within the 7-8 range. These scores combined to produce a mean score of 9.18 and an overall percentage score of 91.75%. The learners' performance is verbally interpreted as "Outstanding," reflecting exceptional achievement and mastery of English proficiency skills.

The results show that ICT integration in writing instruction significantly improves students' proficiency, with most learners demonstrating outstanding performance, likely due to the interactive and adaptive nature of digital tools. Writing apps, grammar checkers, and digital storytelling platforms provided students with immediate feedback and structured practice, enabling them to refine their writing skills more effectively than traditional methods. The flexibility of ICT tools also allowed students to progress at their own pace, fostering confidence and autonomy in the writing process. However, a smaller group of students who struggled may have faced difficulties related to writing fluency, access to technology, or individual learning styles, which limited their ability to fully benefit from these tools. Given this, teachers should maximize ICT's potential by incorporating technology-driven feedback and differentiated instruction while ensuring additional support for students who need targeted writing interventions. Personalized guidance or alternative instructional approaches, such as structured scaffolding or blended learning models, may help bridge the gap and ensure that all students develop strong writing proficiency.

Additionally, it was observed that:

10. "Learners engaged well with the lesson, using Google Docs to write their paragraphs. Many pupils were able to structure their writing effectively, but some struggled with organizing their ideas into a coherent paragraph. While they had a good grasp of descriptive language, a few needed guidance in linking sentences logically and

cohesively. The visual and interactive aspects of Google Docs helped them feel more confident and engaged in the writing process."

- (*Observation No. 1, August 5, 2024 - Writing: Writing a Short Descriptive Paragraph About a Character or Setting in Stories Listened to*)

11. "Learners actively participated in the peer feedback process, and the collaborative use of Padlet allowed them to engage with one another's work in a constructive way. Most of them provided useful feedback, particularly on improving sentence details or adding more sensory descriptions. The use of Padlet encouraged a sense of community in the classroom and helped pupils learn from their peers."

- (*Observation No. 2, August 6, 2024 - Writing: Writing a Short Descriptive Paragraph About a Character or Setting in Stories Listened to*)

12. "Learners were excited to present their new endings and took pride in showcasing their work on PowerPoint Presentation. Many of them made significant improvements in their writing after receiving feedback, and their presentations were full of detail and creativity. The visual aspect of PowerPoint Presentation helped them focus on the structure of their work, and they seemed more confident presenting in front of their peers."

- (*Observation No. 3, August 12, 2024 - Writing: Writing a Short Paragraph Providing Another Ending for a Story Listened To*)

The observations demonstrate that ICT integration significantly enhances writing proficiency by providing collaborative, interactive, feedback-oriented learning experiences. Digital platforms like Google Docs, Padlet, and PowerPoint allowed students to organize their thoughts more effectively, revise their work in real time, and receive constructive peer feedback, resulting in more coherent and well-structured writing. Additionally, visual tools and multimedia elements helped learners develop descriptive writing skills and confidence in self-expression. The ability to edit their work digitally encouraged students to experiment with sentence structures and refine their ideas, fostering a deeper understanding of the writing process. However, some students struggled with organizing their thoughts and linking ideas cohesively, indicating the need for additional scaffolding or guided practice in writing fluency and logical sequencing.

The quantitative results in Table 4 strongly support the impact of ICT integration on writing proficiency, with an overall percentage score of 91.75%, classified as outstanding. 80% of students scoring within the 9-10 range confirms that digital tools provided effective writing support, structured practice, and interactive learning opportunities that contributed to exceptional performance. The observations in Part I align with these findings, highlighting how ICT-enhanced learning environments—featuring real-time editing, multimedia integration, and peer collaboration—helped students develop writing autonomy and refine their skills. However, 20% of learners scoring the 7-8 range suggests that some students may have faced challenges related to writing fluency, access to digital tools, or individual learning styles.

This is consistent with research showing ICT's benefits in enhancing writing proficiency. SciSpace (2024) found that using ICT tools in writing instruction improves students' writing by providing real-time feedback, which helps them quickly correct errors and enhance their writing quality. Egumpp (2024) also emphasized the role of ICT in supporting students with language challenges, highlighting that technology allows for more structured writing practice and aids in developing writing fluency. Additionally, Sarwat (2021) pointed out that ICT helps students become more engaged in the writing process through digital storytelling and collaborative writing platforms, further boosting their proficiency. These findings are supported by Department of Education Order No. 65, s. 2016, which highlights the "Policy Guidelines on the Use of ICT in Teaching and Learning". This order encourages schools to integrate ICT into instruction, promoting digital literacy and writing proficiency.

Part II. English Proficiency Level of the Learners Taught in English without ICT Integration

Table 5. *English Proficiency Level of the Learners Taught in English without ICT Integration in Terms of Vocabulary*

Score Range	Frequency	Percentage	Overall Percentage Score	Mean Score	Interpretation
9 - 10	14	35.00%	79%	7.90	Need Improvement
7 - 8	22	55.00%			
5 - 6	4	10.00%			

Table 5 shows the English proficiency level of the learners taught in English without ICT integration in terms of vocabulary. The data shows three score ranges: 9-10, 7-8, and 5-6. A significant portion of the learners, 22 or 55.00%, scored within the 7-8 range, while 14, representing 35.00%, scored within the 9-10 range. The remaining four learners, or 10.00%, scored within the 5-6 range. These results combined yielded a mean score of 7.9 and an overall percentage score of 79%. The learners' performance in the 9-10 range is verbally interpreted as "Need Improvement," indicating areas where further development or reinforcement may be required to achieve satisfactory proficiency.

The results indicate that students taught without ICT integration demonstrated only moderate vocabulary proficiency, with a significant portion needing improvement, suggesting that traditional teaching methods may not provide the same level of engagement and adaptability as technology-enhanced instruction. Without access to interactive tools like language apps or digital flashcards, students may have had fewer

opportunities for active and personalized vocabulary practice, making retention and comprehension more challenging. The lower scores among some learners highlight the limitations of passive learning approaches, which may not effectively cater to different learning styles or reinforce vocabulary acquisition as dynamically as ICT-based methods. Given this, teachers must explore alternative strategies to enrich vocabulary instruction, such as incorporating vocabulary games, contextualized reading activities, and collaborative exercises that encourage active engagement. While ICT remains a powerful tool for vocabulary development, structured non-digital methods, when designed effectively, can still provide meaningful learning experiences that help bridge the proficiency gap among students.

Also, observations were as follows:

13. "The learners engaged with the lesson as they actively participated in identifying common and proper nouns. However, without digital tools, they struggled with spelling and punctuation. For example, some of them had difficulty remembering to capitalize proper nouns in their sentences, and this went unnoticed until the teacher provided feedback."

- *(Observation No. 1, August 29, 2024 - Vocabulary: Use Common and Proper Nouns in a Sentence)*

14. "Some learners struggled to remember the specific rules for adding /es/ to nouns ending in 's,' 'x,' 'sh,' or 'ch.' For instance, one of them wrote 'two foxes' as 'two fox,' missing the correct plural form. Without digital tools that could check their grammar or provide instant examples, pupils found it difficult to recognize and self-correct their mistakes."

- *(Observation No. 2, September 3, 2024 - Vocabulary: Use Plural Form of Regular Nouns by Adding /s/ or /es/)*

15. "The learners enjoyed sharing their sentences with peers, but several still struggled with capitalization and the difference between common and proper nouns. The teacher provided one-on-one support to help them revise their sentences. Without the use of

ICT tools for instant grammar correction or sentence suggestions, the process of revision was slower."

- *(Observation No. 3, August 30, 2024 - Vocabulary: Use Common and Proper Nouns in a Sentence)*

The observations show the key challenges faced by students learning without ICT integration, particularly in vocabulary retention, self-correction, and spelling accuracy. Without interactive tools like language-learning apps, digital flashcards, or auto-correct features, students struggled to reinforce vocabulary concepts and required continuous teacher intervention to identify and correct errors. Unlike ICT-supported instruction, where learners receive instant feedback, students in the non-ICT group relied solely on delayed teacher feedback, leading to repeated mistakes and slower progress in vocabulary

acquisition. Additionally, the absence of engaging digital exercises meant that students had fewer opportunities for independent exploration, making vocabulary learning more passive. The struggles with spelling, capitalization, and pluralization indicate that traditional methods did not provide enough reinforcement to help learners internalize vocabulary rules effectively.

The quantitative results in Table 5 confirm the lower vocabulary proficiency among students taught without ICT integration, with an overall percentage score of 79% categorized as "Need Improvement." The majority (55%) scored within the 7-8 range, indicating that while some learners demonstrated moderate proficiency, their vocabulary skills were not fully developed. Additionally, 10% of students scored within the 5-6 range, signaling serious gaps in vocabulary knowledge. The observations in Part I align with these findings, emphasizing how the lack of interactive, self-correcting, and engaging learning tools contributed to difficulty in spelling, capitalization, and proper noun usage. The lower scores highlight the limitations of passive learning approaches, which do not reinforce vocabulary retention as effectively as ICT-based methods. To bridge this gap, teachers should implement structured non-digital alternatives, such as contextualized reading activities, vocabulary games, and collaborative exercises, ensuring that students actively engage with new words and develop stronger vocabulary skills despite the absence of ICT tools.

The findings of low performance in vocabulary align with the study of Lastiri (2023), who identified that ineffective vocabulary learning is often caused by passive learning methods and a lack of contextual understanding. Similarly, Gamboa et al. (2021) emphasized that vocabulary acquisition often leads to slower language development when not supported by modern tools or engagement strategies. Likewise, McKeown (2019) pointed out that students often struggle to build a robust vocabulary foundation without collaborative and engaging vocabulary practices. To address this, the Department of Education Order No. 35, s. 2016, which outlines the "Learning Action Cell as a K to 12 Basic Education Program School-Based Continuing Professional Development Strategy for the Improvement of Teaching and Learning", provides a legal basis for improving teaching strategies. This encourages innovative and collaborative teaching practices to support student learning outcomes, including vocabulary development.

Table 6. *English Proficiency Level of the Learners Taught in English without ICT Integration in Terms of Grammar*

Score Range	Frequency	Percentage	Overall Percentage Score	Mean Score	Interpretation
9 - 10	11	27.50%	76.50%	7.650	Need Improvement
7 - 8	19	47.50%			

Table 6 presents the English proficiency level of the learners taught in English without ICT integration in terms of grammar. Most of the learners (27.50%) scored within the 7-8 range, while 27.50% scored within the range of 9-10. However, 25% fell within the range of 5-6. A mean score of 7.65 with an overall percentage score of 76.50% was obtained, described as Need Improvement, indicating areas where further development or reinforcement is necessary to reach satisfactory proficiency levels. The findings show that students taught without ICT integration demonstrated moderate grammar proficiency, with much needing improvement, likely due to the limitations of traditional teaching methods in providing engagement and individualized support. Without access to interactive tools like grammar-checking software or digital exercises, students relied on passive learning approaches, which may have hindered their ability to reinforce grammatical concepts effectively. Those who scored lower likely struggled with insufficient practice and lacked immediate feedback, which technology could have provided. Given this, teachers should explore alternative strategies such as grammar games, sentence diagramming, and peer editing to create more interactive learning experiences. Personalized support for struggling students is also crucial, as conventional methods alone may not address the diverse learning needs required for mastering grammar skills.

16. "Some learners immediately understood the difference between the sentence types, while others struggled to identify the correct sentence type. The lack of ICT tools meant learners had to rely on traditional writing methods, and some of them found it challenging to keep track of the four sentence types while writing their dialogues."

- (*Observation No. 1, August 15, 2024 - Grammar: Using Different Kinds of Sentences in Dialogue*)

17. "Pair work helped learners learn from one another. Many of them struggled with the task, needing extra time to review their dialogue and ensure they had correctly used all four sentence types. Without digital tools for checking their work, pupils had to rely on their own understanding and my guidance."

- (*Observation No. 2, August 16, 2024 - Grammar: Using Different Kinds of Sentences in Dialogue*)

18. "Learners found the revision process helpful, but without the help of digital tools for immediate feedback, the revision process took longer. Some of them struggled to make quick improvements and were hesitant to revise their sentences."

- (*Observation No. 3, August 19, 2024 - Grammar: Using Different Kinds of Sentences in Dialogue*)

The observations reveal that students taught without ICT integration faced challenges in grammar proficiency due to the lack of immediate feedback and interactive

learning support. Without access to grammar-checking tools, sentence-building apps, or interactive revision exercises, learners had difficulty identifying and correcting sentence structure errors on their own. Instead, they relied heavily on teacher guidance and peer support, which slowed the revision process and led to hesitation in making improvements. Additionally, tracking and applying multiple grammatical rules at once proved difficult, particularly for learners who required repeated exposure and reinforcement. The absence of real-time correction and digital practice exercises made grammar learning more passive, causing some students to struggle with understanding sentence types, sentence construction, and revisions.

The quantitative results in Table 6 confirm the low grammar proficiency among students taught without ICT integration, with an overall percentage score of 76.50%, categorized as "Need Improvement." While 47.50% of students scored within the 7-8 range, indicating moderate proficiency, a significant portion (25%) scored within the 5-6 range, highlighting serious struggles with grammatical concepts. The observations align with these findings, as they illustrate how learners lacked real-time feedback and self-correction opportunities, leading to hesitation in revision, difficulty tracking grammar rules, and a slower learning process. The low scores reinforce the need for alternative instructional strategies, such as grammar games, sentence diagramming, peer editing, and structured teacher-led reinforcement, to create engaging, interactive learning experiences that help bridge the proficiency gap. Personalized support for struggling students is also crucial, as conventional methods alone may not provide the individualized practice needed for mastering grammar skills effectively. The low performance in grammar proficiency aligns with the findings of Amanda and Donal (2019), who noted that students often struggle with grammar in non-ICT environments, leading to frequent verb tense and sentence structure errors. Khan et al. (2020) also emphasized that grammar instruction without interactive tools can lower engagement and retention of grammatical rules, leading to learning gaps. Furthermore, Fatimah (2019) highlighted that without access to technology-based grammar tools, students are less likely to develop a deep understanding of how grammatical elements function in various contexts. In the Philippines, Department of Education Order No. 70, s. 2011, which outlines the "Adoption of the National Framework for Professional Development of Teachers," provides a legal basis for addressing these issues. This order promotes continuous professional development for teachers, encouraging them to adopt innovative teaching strategies and improve instruction quality, particularly in challenging areas like grammar.

Table 7. *English Proficiency Level of the Learners Taught in English without ICT Integration in Terms of Reading*

Score Range	Frequency	Percentage	Overall Percentage Score	Mean Score	Interpretation
9 - 10	19	47.50%	82.50%	8.25	Satisfactory
7 - 8	17	42.50%			

Table 7 illustrates the English proficiency level of the learners taught in English without ICT integration in reading. The result revealed that most of the learners (47.50%) scored within the range of 9-10, while 42.50% scored within the 7-8 range. Additionally, 10.00% scored within the 5-6 range. These scores yielded an overall percentage score of 82.5% and a mean score of 8.25, which means they were satisfactory.

The findings show that students taught without ICT integration performed satisfactorily in reading, meeting expected standards but lacking the enhanced engagement and adaptability that digital tools provide. Without interactive e-books, digital comprehension aids, or multimedia resources, students had fewer opportunities for personalized and immediate feedback, which could have helped deepen their understanding of texts. Those who scored lower may have struggled with the passive nature of traditional reading instruction, which does not always cater to varying comprehension levels or learning preferences. Given this, teachers should implement more interactive reading strategies, such as guided reading sessions and collaborative discussions, to make learning more engaging. Providing structured support and scaffolding techniques can also help struggling students develop stronger comprehension skills, ensuring that all learners benefit from effective reading instruction, even without ICT.

Likewise, the teacher observes the following:

19. "While learners were able to identify the 2-syllable words in the story, they struggled with fluency when reading longer sentences. Some of them had difficulty reading the story aloud without pausing awkwardly between syllables."

- (*Observation No. 1, September 19, 2024 - Reading: Read Phrases, Sentences, and Short Stories Consisting of 2-Syllable Words*)

20. "The pupils were fairly engaged in the group reading activity, but without digital support, there was little reinforcement for those who needed additional help with fluency. Interactive, digital tools like reading apps could have allowed for more individualized learning."

- (*Observation No. 2, September 19, 2024 - Reading: Read Phrases, Sentences, and Short Stories Consisting of 2-Syllable Words*)

21. "Without the visual or auditory aids provided by ICT, some pupils struggled to stay engaged, especially those who had difficulty with reading fluency. The lack of interactive feedback meant that they didn't receive immediate correction when they mispronounced words."

- (Observation No. 3, September 23, 2024 - Reading: Read Phrases, Sentences, and Short Stories Consisting of 2-Syllable Words)

The observations indicate that students taught without ICT integration faced difficulties in reading fluency and comprehension, primarily due to the lack of immediate feedback and interactive reinforcement. Traditional reading instruction, while effective for some, did not provide struggling students with personalized support, making it harder for them to correct pronunciation errors and improve fluency. The absence of digital reading tools such as audiobooks, interactive texts, and comprehension apps meant that learners who needed additional help had to rely solely on teacher feedback, which was limited and time-consuming. Additionally, the passive nature of reading activities without digital engagement led to decreased motivation, particularly for learners who required visual and auditory reinforcement to fully understand and retain the material.

The quantitative data in Table 7 confirms that students taught without ICT integration achieved a "Satisfactory" proficiency level in reading, with an overall percentage score of 82.5%. While 47.50% of students scored in the 9-10 range, indicating proficiency in reading skills, 42.50% fell within the 7-8 range, suggesting that a significant number of students still struggled with fluency and comprehension. Furthermore, 10% of students scored within the 5-6 range, highlighting reading difficulties that require additional support. The observations in Part I align with these findings, as they illustrate that students who lacked access to ICT tools had trouble with fluency, self-correction, and motivation. To address these challenges, teachers should implement more interactive non-digital strategies, such as guided reading, structured discussions, and peer-assisted learning, to engage students and provide targeted support for those who struggle with fluency and comprehension.

The findings are supported by the study of Nowak (2021), which found that students without ICT tools often struggle with reading comprehension due to the lack of interactive and adaptive resources that make reading more engaging. Similarly, Raghbdoust and Malekmohammadi (2023) highlighted that the absence of technology in reading instruction can result in slower development of critical reading skills, as students are not exposed to the varied contexts that digital tools provide. Moreover, Chanco (2023) emphasized that regular methods often fall short of keeping students engaged, particularly when reading challenging or unfamiliar texts. These issues are addressed in Department of Education Order No. 35, s. 2016, which supports the "Learning Action Cell as a K to 12 Basic Education Program School-Based Continuing Professional Development Strategy for the Improvement of Teaching and Learning." This policy encourages continuous teacher development and the exploration of innovative teaching strategies, providing a framework for improving instruction in reading, even in environments without ICT integration. By fostering collaborative learning among teachers and promoting best practices in reading instruction, the policy aims to enhance student reading proficiency and overall literacy development.

Table 8. *English Proficiency Level of the Learners Taught in English without ICT Integration in Terms of Writing*

Score Range	Frequency	Percentage	Overall Percentage Score	Mean Score	Interpretation
9 - 10	8	20.00%	74%	7.4	Need Improvement
7 - 8	21	52.50%			
5 - 6	11	27.50%			

Table 8 presents the English proficiency level of the learners taught in English without ICT integration in terms of writing with a mean score of 7.4, described as needing improvement, indicating areas where further development or reinforcement is necessary to achieve satisfactory proficiency levels. Statistics show that 52.50% of the learners scored within the range of 7-8. However, 27.50% scored within the 5-6 range and 20% fell within the 7-10.

The findings show that students taught without ICT integration demonstrated moderate writing proficiency, with many struggling to develop essential skills due to the lack of interactive and feedback-driven learning opportunities. Without access to digital writing tools such as grammar checkers, collaborative platforms, and automated feedback systems, students may have limited chances to refine their writing, organize ideas effectively, and correct mistakes in real time. Those in the lower range likely needed more structured support, as traditional teaching methods alone may not have been enough to strengthen their proficiency. Given this, teachers should incorporate alternative strategies like peer reviews, guided writing exercises, and structured feedback sessions to help students improve their writing. More targeted interventions may also be necessary for struggling learners, ensuring they receive personalized support to develop their writing skills effectively.

Additionally, observations were as follows:

22. "Learners seemed to understand the task and began working on their paragraphs, but many needed reminders to include sensory details. Without access to ICT tools, pupils were more focused on writing by hand, which took longer for some of them. Some of them struggled to organize their thoughts and were hesitant to write detailed descriptions."

- (Observation No. 1, August 5, 2024 - Writing: Writing a Short Descriptive Paragraph About a Character or Setting in Stories Listened To)

23. "The peer feedback session worked well in helping learners identify areas for improvement in their writing. Many of them were able to make significant revisions to their paragraphs, adding more vivid descriptions. However, some of them struggled with providing specific, actionable feedback to their peers, and without digital tools, the process was slower."

- (Observation No. 2, August 6, 2024 - Writing: Writing a Short Descriptive Paragraph About a Character or Setting in Stories Listened To)

24. "Sharing their work aloud was a highlight for most learners, and it gave them a sense of pride in their writing. However, some of them struggled with reading their work aloud due to lack of confidence, and the absence of ICT tools made it harder for them to correct errors before presenting." (

- Observation No. 3, August 12, 2024 - Writing: Writing a Short Paragraph Providing Another Ending for a Story Listened To)

The observations reveal that students taught without ICT integration struggled with organizing ideas, providing specific feedback, and refining their writing efficiently. Without digital writing tools such as grammar checkers, collaborative platforms, and automated feedback systems, students found it difficult to identify and correct mistakes in real-time, leading to slower progress and repeated errors. The lack of ICT also resulted in less engagement and lower confidence, as learners were hesitant to expand on their ideas or make significant revisions. Additionally, peer feedback sessions were slower and less effective, as students lacked structured digital support to guide their revisions. This indicates that traditional methods alone may not be enough to reinforce key writing skills, and students need additional structured support to develop proficiency in writing organization, fluency, and coherence.

The quantitative data in Table 8 confirms that students taught without ICT integration had low writing proficiency, with an overall percentage score of 74%, categorized as "Need Improvement." While 52.50% of students scored in the 7-8 range, indicating moderate writing proficiency, 27.50% scored within the 5-6 range, highlighting serious challenges with writing fluency, organization, and detail development. The observations align with these findings, as they illustrate how students lacked immediate feedback, struggled with self-editing, and had difficulty expanding their ideas. The low scores reinforce the need for alternative strategies, such as peer review with structured guidance, guided writing exercises, and teacher-led interventions, to help struggling students refine their writing skills. Implementing more personalized support and structured scaffolding techniques can help bridge the gap and ensure that all students reach satisfactory proficiency in writing.

This aligns with the study of Sarwat (2021), who pointed out that students without ICT tools often struggle with writing due to the lack of immediate feedback and creative

engagement, which are crucial for developing strong writing skills. SciSpace (2024) also emphasized that the absence of technology in writing instruction can result in slower improvement, as students miss out on opportunities for interactive learning and personalized feedback. Mohamed (2022) similarly noted that without digital tools, students may face more significant challenges in organizing their thoughts and improving their grammar, leading to lower performance. In the Philippines, Department of Education Order No. 42, s. 2017, which outlines the “National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers,” provides a legal framework supporting continuous teacher development in improving instructional strategies. This policy emphasizes the importance of adopting innovative teaching methods to meet diverse learning needs, including enhancing writing instruction. It encourages teachers to explore new strategies and interventions to boost student writing performance.

Table 9. *Summary of the English Proficiency Level of the Learners Taught in English with and without ICT Integration*

English Proficiency Aspect	With ICT Integration			Without ICT Integration		
	Overall Percentage Score	Mean Score	Interpretation	Overall Percentage Score	Mean Score	Interpretation
Vocabulary	90.75%	9.08	Outstanding	79.00%	7.90	Need Improvement
Grammar	91.25%	9.12	Outstanding	76.50	7.65	Need Improvement
Reading	91.00%	9.10	Outstanding	82.50	8.25	Satisfactory
Writing	91.75%	9.18	Outstanding	74.00%	7.40	Need Improvement
Total	91.19%	9.12	Outstanding	78.00%	7.80	Need Improvement

Table 9 summarizes the English proficiency level of the learners taught in English with and without ICT integration. It shows that learners taught with ICT integration demonstrated outstanding achievement across all aspects of proficiency. Writing emerged as the highest-scoring area, achieving an overall percentage score of 91.75% and a mean score of 9.18. Grammar was closely followed, with an overall percentage score of 91.25% and a mean score of 9.12, reflecting exceptional proficiency. Reading scored 91%, with a mean of 9.10, indicating outstanding performance. Vocabulary recorded an overall percentage score of 90.75% and a mean score of 9.08, reinforcing the mastery of vocabulary skills. Overall, the total score for learners taught with ICT integration was 91.19%, with a mean of 91.12, categorizing their performance as

outstanding across the board. In contrast, learners taught without ICT integration exhibited a need for improvement. Reading was the highest scoring aspect, with an overall percentage of 82.05% and a mean score of 8.25, falling to the satisfactory range. Vocabulary followed with a score of 79.00% and a mean of 7.9, indicating areas needing further development. Grammar scored 76.50% with a mean of 7.65, signaling the necessity for improvement, while writing recorded the lowest score at 74.00% and a mean of 7.40, highlighting significant areas requiring attention. The total score for learners taught without ICT integration was 78.00%, indicating considerable room for growth across all proficiency aspects.

The findings demonstrate a clear advantage for learners taught with ICT integration, as their consistently higher scores in writing, grammar, reading, and vocabulary highlight the effectiveness of technology-enhanced instruction in fostering deeper learning and engagement. The superior performance of these students suggests that ICT tools provide interactive, adaptive, and feedback-driven experiences that support language mastery, whereas the lower scores of students taught without ICT reveal gaps in proficiency that traditional teaching methods may not fully address. This contrast underscores the need for more innovative instructional approaches that cater to diverse learning needs and ensure all students develop strong language skills. Given this, integrating ICT in language instruction should be a priority, as it not only enhances comprehension and retention but also encourages students to take ownership of their learning while developing essential digital literacy. Teachers must embrace technology as a core component of their strategies, and professional development in ICT integration is crucial to equipping educators with the skills needed to maximize its benefits, ultimately creating a more dynamic and effective learning environment.

This is also evident in the study of Caner and Aydın (2021), which found that ICT in English can boost motivation and involvement. Digital tools can enhance language learning by providing interactive and multimedia features and increase motivation and commitment. ICT can help learners learn English through material and activities that suit their needs and interests—finally, using ICT to teach and learn English as a Second Language benefits teachers and learners (Simbolon et al., 2019). ICT may improve English proficiency in many ways, from interactive language learning tools to specific training and collaboration. As technology advances, instructors and learners can use ICT to improve English language learning (Abel et al., 2022).

Part III. Significant Difference in the English Proficiency Level of the Learners Taught in English Using ICT and those Taught in English without Using ICT

Table 10. *Mann Whitney U test on Testing the Normality for the Significant Difference in the English Proficiency Level of the Learners Taught in English Using ICT and those Taught in English without Using ICT*

Groups	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.

Experiment	.478	40	.000	.517	40	.000
Controlled	.222	40	.000	.894	40	.001

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Table 10 presents the results of the Mann-Whitney U test used to assess the normality of the English proficiency levels of learners taught in English with ICT integration and learners taught in English without ICT integration. Two normality tests, Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk, were applied to the experimental group (learners taught with ICT) and the controlled group (learners taught without ICT). For the experimental group, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistic is 0.478, with a significance value of 0.000, while the Shapiro-Wilk statistic is 0.517, with a significance value of 0.000. Both significance values are below 0.05, indicating that the data for the experimental group is not normally distributed. Similarly, for the controlled group, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistic is 0.222 with a significance value of 0.000, and the Shapiro-Wilk statistic is 0.894 with a significance value of 0.001.

These results indicate that the data for the controlled group is also not normally distributed. The findings from these tests suggest that the assumption of normality has been violated for both groups, supporting the need for non-parametric tests, such as the Mann-Whitney U test, for further analysis.

Table 11. Hypothesis Test Summary on the Significant Difference in the English Proficiency Level of the Learners Taught in English Using ICT and those Taught in English without Using ICT

Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
The distribution of Experiment is the same across categories of Controlled	Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test	.000	Reject the Null Hypothesis

*Asymptotic significance is displayed. The significance level is .05.

As described in Table 11, the hypothesis test summary on the significant difference in the English proficiency levels between learners taught in English with ICT integration and those taught without ICT integration. The null hypothesis stated that the distribution of the experimental group (learners taught with ICT) was the same as that of the control group (learners taught without ICT). The results from the Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test show a significance value of 0.000, which is below the threshold of 0.05. As a result, the decision is to reject the null hypothesis, indicating a statistically significant difference in the English proficiency levels between the two groups.

The results of the Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U Test confirm a statistically significant difference in English proficiency levels between students taught

with ICT integration and those taught without it, demonstrating that ICT-based instruction leads to higher proficiency in vocabulary, grammar, reading, and writing. The rejection of the null hypothesis suggests that ICT tools, such as interactive learning platforms, personalized feedback systems, and multimedia resources, significantly enhance language learning by making it more engaging and adaptive. In contrast, students without ICT exposure may have lacked access to such dynamic learning environments, limiting their opportunities for deeper comprehension and skill development. Given these findings, students benefit greatly from ICT integration as it provides a flexible and interactive learning experience, allowing them to practice language skills at their own pace while reinforcing retention through immediate feedback and diverse resources. For teachers, these results highlight the necessity of incorporating digital tools into language instruction to foster better engagement and improved learning outcomes. However, for classrooms without ICT access, blended learning approaches or more innovative non-digital strategies should be explored to help bridge the proficiency gap and ensure all students receive effective language instruction.

These findings are supported by Khan and Kuddus (2020), who emphasized the positive effects of ICT in enhancing student engagement and improving language proficiency through interactive and autonomous learning tools. Tang et al. (2021) also highlighted that integrating ICT significantly boosts student outcomes by promoting active learning and providing immediate feedback, which helps learners correct errors and develop language skills more efficiently. Additionally, Sabiri (2020) pointed out that regular teaching methods without ICT may limit the opportunities for students to engage with language materials in meaningful and varied ways, leading to lower proficiency levels. In the Philippines, Department of Education Order No. 78, s. 2010, which focuses on "Strengthening the Integration of ICT in Basic Education," supports the findings by emphasizing the role of technology in enhancing teaching and learning outcomes. The order mandates the integration of ICT into the curriculum to improve student learning experiences and outcomes, particularly in language instruction, aligning with the study's results that ICT significantly contributes to higher English proficiency levels.

Part IV. ICT-Based Instructional Model in English Could be Developed Based on the Findings of the Study

The study's findings demonstrate the effectiveness of ICT tools in enhancing English language instruction, highlighting both the benefits and challenges of technology integration. Students showed increased engagement, autonomy, and performance when using ICT tools like language learning apps and interactive reading platforms. However, some students struggled with distractions and technical challenges. These insights indicate the need for an ICT-based instructional model that combines adaptive learning, immediate feedback, collaboration, and structured support. The model should also utilize

widely accessible tools such as PowerPoint presentations, videos, learning platforms, and mobile applications to create a comprehensive learning experience.

A central component of this model should be using computer applications and adaptive learning technologies that allow students to learn at their own pace. These apps help students practice vocabulary, reading, and listening skills while receiving instant feedback on their progress. Incorporating mobile and computer apps into the classroom allows students to continue learning outside of regular settings, increasing engagement and access to learning resources. Additionally, these applications are accessible and user-friendly, making them ideal tools for developing English proficiency.

PowerPoint presentations and videos should also be part of the instructional model. PowerPoint is a versatile tool that allows teachers to visually present grammar rules, vocabulary, and reading comprehension techniques in a structured manner. Its ability to incorporate text, images, audio, and video makes it highly engaging for students. Along with PowerPoint, the inclusion of educational videos provides a dynamic way to explain complex topics. The study findings showed that students who used video tutorials for grammar exercises performed better than those who relied solely on textbooks. Therefore, teachers should incorporate relevant educational videos to clarify complex concepts, improve comprehension, and make learning more interactive and engaging.

Learning platforms like Google Classroom should be incorporated into the model to facilitate interaction and track student progress. These platforms allow for the seamless integration of assignments, quizzes, and reading tasks while providing collaborative learning spaces through discussion forums and shared documents. Teachers can use learning platforms to upload PowerPoint slides and video tutorials for students to access, even outside of class. These platforms also support communication between students and teachers, encouraging students to ask questions and participate more actively in their learning process. The platforms offer grading tools and progress trackers that allow teachers to monitor individual student performance and identify areas that need reinforcement. Mobile devices and cellphone applications should be integrated into the model as an essential tool for language learning, offering flexibility and accessibility. Many students already possess smartphones, which makes it easier to incorporate applications that reinforce their learning in real-world contexts. Teachers can assign tasks through mobile applications, such as listening exercises, vocabulary quizzes, and short reading assignments that can be completed on the go.

To ensure the success of this ICT-based model, it is crucial to address potential distractions and technical challenges. The study highlighted the issue of students becoming distracted by non-academic content during lessons. To counter this, the model should incorporate strategies to manage and minimize distractions, such as monitoring tools available on learning platforms that allow teachers to supervise student activity. Teachers can also guide students in using time management apps, which can help them stay focused and limit their exposure to distractions while working on assignments. Structured training sessions for students and teachers on effectively using ICT tools will be vital in overcoming technical challenges and ensuring smooth integration. Lastly, the ICT-based instructional model for English should combine adaptive learning through

mobile apps, interactive PowerPoint presentations, educational videos, learning platforms, and mobile devices. This model addresses the study's findings and ensures students receive personalized, engaging, and flexible learning experiences.

The study's findings align with existing research that highlights the effectiveness of ICT tools in enhancing English language instruction through increased student engagement, autonomy, and improved performance while also acknowledging challenges such as distractions and technical issues. The integration of multimedia tools, adaptive learning applications, and digital platforms is essential in creating an effective instructional model that maximizes ICT's benefits. PowerPoint presentations, for instance, have been found to significantly improve engagement and comprehension when used effectively in English instruction, as they allow teachers to present structured lessons incorporating text, images, and videos that make learning more interactive (Dewi & Kareviati, 2021). Additionally, video-based learning has been shown to enhance student understanding, particularly in grammar instruction, where students who used video tutorials performed better than those who relied solely on traditional textbooks (Feng & Wang, 2023). This highlights the importance of integrating visual and auditory learning aids in instructional models to make complex language concepts more accessible. Furthermore, learning platforms such as Google Classroom or other online management systems provide structured environments for students to collaborate, complete assignments, and receive timely feedback, ensuring consistent learning engagement beyond the classroom (Ginaya et al., 2020). These platforms allow teachers to monitor progress, provide instant feedback, and facilitate student discussions, fostering a more student-centered approach to English learning. However, the challenge of student distractions from non-academic content remains a critical issue, reinforcing the need for monitoring tools and structured digital literacy training to help students stay focused and use technology responsibly. Integrating mobile applications into the instructional model can also enhance accessibility and flexibility in learning, as students can complete exercises, practice vocabulary, and engage with language tasks on their own time, reinforcing skills outside of the classroom. Given these insights, an ICT-based instructional model should incorporate adaptive learning, multimedia tools, mobile applications, and interactive platforms, while implementing strategies to manage distractions and provide structured ICT training, ensuring that technology serves as an enabler rather than a hindrance in language learning.

Conclusions

From the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

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1. Most learners taught in English with ICT integration achieved outstanding proficiency levels across all language domains, including vocabulary, grammar, reading, and writing. The overall mean scores consistently fell within the "Outstanding"

range, indicating that ICT integration significantly enhanced learners' English language proficiency.

2. Learners taught without ICT integration showed lower proficiency levels than those taught with ICT. Most learners fell within the "Needs Improvement" range for vocabulary, grammar, and writing, with reading being the only area where learners demonstrated "Satisfactory" proficiency. This highlights the effectiveness of ICT in improving English language outcomes.

3. The results of the Mann-Whitney U Test indicated a statistically significant difference in English proficiency levels between learners taught with ICT and those taught without. Learners who used ICT in their English instruction performed better across all language domains, confirming the effectiveness of ICT Integration in developing the English Proficiency Level of the Learners. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

4. Based on the findings, an ICT-based instructional model incorporating adaptive learning technologies, multimedia tools, learning platforms, and mobile devices was developed. This model promotes personalized, interactive, and flexible learning experiences while addressing potential distractions through monitoring tools and structured training for learners and teachers.

Recommendations

The results of this research led to the formulation of the following recommendations:

1. Based on the findings of the study, the learners taught in English with ICT Integration got an Outstanding proficiency level in all domains. To maintain and further enhance their performance, it is recommended that schools continue to integrate a variety of ICT tools in English instruction, including language learning apps, interactive reading platforms, and multimedia resources. Teachers may also explore new technologies and innovative teaching strategies that leverage ICT to ensure learners remain engaged and challenged at their respective proficiency levels.

2. According to the result of the post-test, the proficiency level of the learners taught in English without ICT Integration in English in terms of vocabulary, grammar and writing was Need Improvement while in reading was satisfactory. With this, it is recommended that ICT tools be gradually introduced into their English language instruction for learners who are taught without ICT integration and demonstrate lower proficiency levels. Teachers can start by incorporating mobile apps, educational videos, and interactive platforms to enhance vocabulary, grammar, and writing skills. Well-developed support should ensure a smooth transition and boost learners' proficiency in these areas.

3. Given the statistically significant difference in proficiency between learners taught with and without ICT integration, it is recommended that schools prioritize the

integration of ICT in English language instruction across all classes. School administrators should allocate resources for training teachers on effective ICT use and invest in necessary technology infrastructure to ensure that all learners benefit from enhanced learning experiences.

4. The result of the study proven that the learners' English proficiency level was being developed by using of ICT Integration. And it is recommended that, the schools may incorporate ICT learning technologies, multimedia tools, and collaborative learning platforms into the curriculum as the learners need. Monitoring tools may be utilized to track learner progress, and regular training sessions for teachers and learners may be conducted to address challenges such as distractions and varying levels of ICT proficiency.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

As the author of this study, the researcher affirms the commitment to maintaining the highest ethical standards throughout the research process. In compliance with ethical guidelines, she ensured that all respondents provided informed consent prior to participation in the study, with clear information about the purpose, procedures, and potential risks involved. She respected the respondents' autonomy by guaranteeing their freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without any negative consequences. Furthermore, the anonymity of all participants was rigorously maintained, and personal identifiers were not disclosed at any point during or after the study.

She prioritized the well-being of the respondents by implementing measures to safeguard their physical and emotional safety throughout the research process. Additionally, we confirm that there were no conflicts of interest in the conduct of this study, ensuring that the research was carried out with integrity and objectivity. She also affirms that plagiarism was strictly avoided, and all sources were appropriately cited to give credit to original authors and works.

Throughout the study, she adhered to impartiality and avoided any form of bias in the interpretation and presentation of the findings. The results of this research were used exclusively for academic purposes and are intended to contribute to the advancement of knowledge in the field.

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